

A WORLD FULL OF SOUNDS.
PAUSANIAS' SACRED SOUNDSCAPE OF BOEOTIA

"To hear with eyes belongs to love's fine wit"

W. Shakespeare, Sonnet XXIII

"A man may see how this world goes with no eyes. Look with thine ears"

W. Shakespeare, King Lear, Act Four, Part Three

Pausanias' *Periegesis* has indeed been defined as a perfect intersection of historical-mythological accounts and geographical narrative since echoes of a past made of events, legends, rites, cults, and interesting trivia merge into the description of Greek natural and cultural landmarks¹. The result is 'a magnificent epitomy', to paraphrase Domenico Musti's words², in which around a focal nucleus, i.e. a journey around mainland Greece, other (virtual) tours of different length branch out in the shape of specific insights and digressions. According to this approach, inspired by Herodotus³, Pausanias manages to create a picture of a still-living and viable cultural past as it is connected deeply with the *realia* of his time. When examining his chain of digressions and descriptions, it seems almost axiomatic that one's attention is drawn immediately to the visual aspects that inevitably stand out. In a literary culture like the contemporary one, where our history is primarily preserved by written evidence and reading and writing are widely used⁴, the eye and the imagination of the reader are easily captured by the rich-in-details images provided by the geographer, who reconstructed through his itinerary the historical and cultural past of mainland Greece⁵.

Although sight is undeniably the predominante sense exploited in any description of places, sites, and contexts⁶, we must bear in mind, however, that Pausanias' *Periegetis*, as any geographical narrative, is by definition the product of a multisensorial experience of individual(s) taking into account different issues, such as orientation, spatial relation, and the character of the places visited. In this respect, thus, all the senses, not only sight, are

¹ GARTLAND 2016, p. 97; COHEN 2001, p. 95; HAWES 2021, p. 1.

² MUSTI 1984, pp. 9-10.

³ MUSTI 1982, pp. xxiv-xxv; xliii-xlvii; HAWES 2016b; BRYANT KIRKLAND 2022, pp. 296-330. Pausanias also follows Herodotus in his hodological approach, according to which the selective description of places responds to the perception and experience of the narrator and not its real position on the map (on the hodological space still fundamental JANNI 1984, pp. 79-158, on Herodotus' narrative base on hodological and not cartographic space see PURSE 2010, pp. 144-150 (with previous bibliography).

⁴ ONG 1971, pp. xx-yy a literary culture it differs from oral culture as the latter preserves its history in stories remembered and recited by its people as a spoke history, not relying to any great degree on reading and writing in everyday life.

⁵ On the debate of Pausanias' ancient audience see KONSTAN 2014 with previous bibliography.

⁶ ONG 1971, pp. xx-yy.